

Exploring inclusiveness in the Engineering student experience at UoA

Focus Group Questions

A number of semi-structured focus groups (3-6 participants, 90-120min) will be conducted as a follow-up to the questionnaire. These will help provide more details and examples from students around their experiences and their sense of belonging in the faculty, as well as provide an opportunity for us to discover any other important factors to consider in future research.

The questions below are indicative of what we intend to ask, and any additional questions that may be needed will be similar to these in order to gain more detail or insight into the experiences that may be described.

Warm up questions (10min)

- How have you made friends so far in the faculty?
- What extracurricular activities do you do with your friends?
- What student clubs/societies are you currently part of?

Student experience questions (50min)

- Tell us about any positive experiences you have had in your Engineering courses/papers.
 - Tell us about any negative experiences you have had in your Engineering courses/papers.
- Probes/sub questions if needed:
- What was it about these experiences that made them positive / negative?
 - If no experiences are being shared, probe about experiences in lab work, lectures, group work, social activities, etc.
- Describe any instances when you have felt confident in yourself or your ability to be an engineer.
 - Describe any instances when you have doubted yourself or your ability to be an engineer.

Probes/sub questions if needed:

- What hurdles or challenges have you faced during your studies so far?
- How did you overcome them?
- Describe any instances when you have thought of leaving Engineering.
- What (or who) has influenced your decision to continue in Engineering?
- How relevant do you think is what you are learning in Engineering to the real world?

Inclusiveness questions (20min)

- Tell us about a time you felt like you 'fit' in the Faculty (use departments for Parts 2-4).
- Tell us about a time you felt like you didn't 'fit' in the Faculty (use departments for Parts 2-4).

Probes/sub questions if needed:

- What/who in the Faculty makes you feel like you do / do not belong?
- What can the Faculty keep doing to improve your sense of belonging or fitting in here?
- What can the Faculty start doing to improve your sense of belonging or fitting in here?

What can the Faculty stop doing to improve your sense of belonging or fitting in here?

- Is there anything we have not covered that you would like to talk about? **(10min)**

Extra questions if there is time:

- Why did you decide to study Engineering?
- What do you think an engineer does at work?
- When did you decide on your specialisation?
- How different is your current specialisation from your original intention?
- If you changed specialisations, why did you change?
- Who or what helped you decide what specialisation to study?
- How do you define "success" in an engineering career?
- How well are you developing the skills you think you need to achieve "success"?